

Use and Misuse of Statistics in Biological Sciences

Dr. (Mrs.) W. G. S. Konarasinghe

Institute of Mathematics & Management, Sri Lanka

sinasisi@gmail.com

Statistics is a science concerned with uncertainty in real life. Probability is the key element of developing it. Statistics depends on mathematics, but it is not a part of mathematics. Like in other disciplines; physics, engineering, chemistry, computer science etc., mathematics is a tool used to solve statistical problems. However, defining statistics as, “Mathematics of uncertainty” is not a bad practice. Statistics plays a vital role in scientific research. It involves in developing and studying methods for; collecting, analyzing, evaluating, interpreting and presenting information. Hence, research and management of large number of fields; Agriculture, Medicine, Biology, Engineering, Business, Economics and many more rely on statistics. Yet, most of the studies are not really benefited from statistics due to misuse of it. A misuse of statistics is a pattern of unsound statistical analysis. Misuse can be a result of; mistakes or negligence, lack of statistics knowledge or purposive. Statisticians suggest that, at least half the papers published in biology contain serious statistical mistakes. Yet Biology is the science of life!

Statistics is divided into two main parts; Descriptive Statistics and Inferential Statistics. In descriptive statistics, sample data are analyzed by measures of location and measures of dispersion. This part of the analysis leads to inferential Statistics, which generalizes statistical findings to population. Hence, reliability of inferences highly depends on the sample statistics. In other words, poorly estimated sample statistics leads to unreliable inferences. As such, using proper techniques in data collection and data analysis are equally important. For example, if the data are not from a random sample, then the descriptive statistics become biased estimates for population parameters; probability estimates become unrealistic and so on. Unfortunately, this is the mostly reported misuse in Biological studies. Another serious issue is not paying attention for the measurement scale of data, when estimating measurements of location and dispersion. For

instance, if the measurement scale is ordinal, then the sample mean and the sample standard deviation are not appropriate measurements, yet they are the blindly used techniques by most of the researchers. The correlation analysis and regression analysis are popular tools in estimation and forecasting. Yet, the Karl Pearson's correlation is used when the Spearman's rank correlation is a must; Linear regression models are fitted when data shows non linear relationships; Multiple regression models are recommended, when Logistic regression is the correct technique. In model based analysis, it is a must to; test model assumptions, test multicollinearity; model validation and model verification, but they are just ignored. Amidst all, "P-Value hackers" abuse statistics for their benefit. Whether the root cause for misusing statistics is negligence, lack of knowledge or any other, the outcome of it is not different. Hence the possible damage to the society is same. Therefore, it is essential to pay attention on stopping misuse of statistics.